

IR42, IR2823-399-5-6, IR9129-163-3-2-2, IR9129-192-2-3-5, and IR2307-247-2-2-3. Nematodes were found in all samples.

Populations in 50-gram root samples

of local varieties ranged from 12 to 380 at tillering, increasing to 50 to 7,000 at flowering, and to 300 to 7,500 at ripening. In the second crop, populations at transplanting were 204 to 9,000; at tiller-

ing, 860 to 11,200.

Populations in 100-ml soil samples averaged 71 throughout the sampling period, with a range of 5 to 450 nematodes. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Using check varieties to adjust visual scores for nonuniform soil drying in drought resistance field screening

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In many areas of monsoon Asia, the dry season allows use of irrigation (surface or sprinkler) to control timing (growth stage) and duration of water stress in drought resistance screening of germplasm in the field. But variability in soil drying results in problems in interpreting visual scores among entries. Using soil moisture measurements (tensiometers, gypsum blocks, or gravimetric sampling) to indicate relative soil water deficits within a field has inherent technical problems and is not generally satisfactory.

A method using frequently spaced check varieties to adjust or normalize field screening results for heterogeneity of soil drying has been developed.

Field screening for drought resistance was conducted in the 1980 dry season at the Klong Luang Rice Experiment Station, Thailand. Localized deviations of IR20 (susceptible check) and BKN6986-108-3 (local resistant check) from their overall means were used to adjust scores of entries in nearby plots. The figure illustrates the heterogeneity of soil drying across the field that was identified by the response of check varieties and deviations from their respective overall means.

Variation in soil drying across field is illustrated by changes in responses of IR20 (susceptible check) and BKN6986-108-3 (resistant check). IRRI.

Statistical analysis of original (A) and adjusted (B) visual drought resistance scores of 77 entries in 1980 dry season field screening for drought resistance at Klong Luang Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

	$\frac{\sigma_v^2}{\sigma_E^2}$	CV (%)	F-value	DMRT (5%) discrimination range (no.)
A	0.5603	29.9	2.12**	A-G (7)
B	1.0377	24.0	3.08**	A-M (13)

At any place in the field, the average of the check varieties' deviations from their respective means was applied to the scores of adjacent entries, normalizing varietal response for soil moisture heterogeneity. The ratio of varietal variance (σ_v^2) to experimental variance (σ_E^2) was used in evaluating the capability of adjusted data to better differentiate entries. Adjusting the original visual drought resistance scores for field soil moisture conditions increased the σ_v^2/σ_E^2 ratio, decreased the CV, and increased the capability of Duncan's Multiple Range Test (5% level) to differentiate between entries (see table).

This method uses check varieties which are usually well known by the individual scorer to systematically cope with the problem of inherent variability in drought screening caused by non-

uniform soil physical properties or by inequity of irrigation water distribution. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Varietal tolerance for acid sulfate soils in North Vietnam

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Varieties were screened for acid sulfate soil tolerance during the 1977, 1978, and

1979 dry seasons at Haiphong, 100 km east of Hanoi. Soils had pH 3.1-3.4 with 4.45-6.20 meq exchangeable aluminum (Al)/ 100 g.

The 245 varieties and lines screened were selected from among local germ-plasm and IRRI lines tolerant of salinity, drought, iron (Fe) toxicity, and phosphorus (P) deficiency. Iron toxicity was evaluated on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale 4 and 8 weeks after transplanting.

Most tolerant of acid sulfate soils were local varieties Bâu, Pokkali, Cut, Cuom, and Chiêm da. (Table 1). Most tolerant lines were IR2151-96-1-5-3, IR2153-26-3-5-6, IR1529-680-3-2, and B9C-Md-3-3.

Tolerance for Al and Fe toxicity and P deficiency was tested among 15 varieties and lines at Thanh tô experiment station. Al toxicity was determined by soaking germinated seeds in 3 and 30 mg Al/ liter soil solution. Fe toxicity and P deficiency tests were done in pots.

Local variety Bâu was tolerant of all three factors (Table 2). IR2151-96-1-5-2, which was less tolerant in the field at 8 weeks, also was less tolerant of iron.

A close relationship was found between Al toxicity and P deficiency (correlation coefficient 0.747). Tolerances for Al and Fe toxicity were not related (correlation coefficient 0.299).

One month after transplanting, with soil pH 4.0 and Al in the soil solution at 7.8 mg/ liter, field evaluation scores correlated with Al toxicity tolerance ($r = 0.917$). But 2 months after transplanting, with soil pH 4.9, field evaluation scores did not correlate with Fe toxicity tolerance ($r = 0.376$), probably because both factors had some influence.

IR lines with IR1416-131-5, CR94-13, and Indonesian variety Sigadis in their parentage are tolerant of Fe toxicity. In these studies, tolerance of Al toxicity and P deficiency seemed to be related to the presence of Sigadis genes. It appears that acid soil tolerance is related to tolerance for Al toxicity, Fe toxicity, and P deficiency.

Three varieties — IR2151-96-1-5-3, IR2153-26-3-56, and B9C-Md-3-3 were selected for yield trials in North Vietnam. IR2153 also can be cultivated

Table 1. Field scores^a of representative varieties and lines in varietal screening on acid sulfate soils^b in North Vietnam.

Variety or line	Score	Variety or line	Score
CSSR-1	5	IR40	4
IR2058-78-1-3-2-3 (IR46)	5	IR42	5
IR2061-464-24-46	5	312151-598-3-5-5	4
IET5233	8	IR2863-38-1	3-4
BG94-1	6	IR4227-164-1-1	6
IR1529-430-2	7	IR4613-54-5	9
IR2053-160-1-2-2	5	B9C-Md-3-3	2-3
IR2070-719-3-5	6	IR1529-430-3	3
IR2153-26-3-5-2	3	IR1750-F5B-5	4-5
IR2053-436-1-2	7	IR2035-117-3	5
K149	4-5	IR2035-242-1	5
Pokkali	2	IR2061-522-6-9	7
M1-48	8	IR3839-1	4-5
IR28	9	IR3880-13	8
IR2153-43-2-5-3	4	IR3880-17	4
IR2071-586-5-6-34	5	IR9575	3
IR2153-26-3-5-6	2	IRAT13	3
IR2823-399-56	6	C22	3
IR4573-4-3-7-14	6	C46-151IR24 ²	4
IR4595-4-1-13	6	IR36	5-6
IR4630-22-2-17	8	A4	3
IR4763-73-1-11	7	IR8	7
IR1514A-E666	5-6	386 (NN75-7)	7
IR2031-2384-1-3-2	3-4	Bâu	1
IR26	6	cut	2
IR2061-214-2-24-1	6	Cuom	2
IR1529-680-3-2	2-3	424 (NN75-2)	5
IR994-102-2-3-2-2-2	5	Sai duong	4-5
IR2151-190-3-5-5	5	Chiêm da	2
IR2151-96-1-5-3	2	B541-bkn-19-34	3

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = growth and tillering nearly normal, 9 = almost all plants dead or dying. ^bMean of 3 dry seasons.

Table 2. Tolerance^a for acid sulfate soils and other stresses of different varieties and lines in greenhouse tests in North Vietnam.

Variety or line	Acid sulfate soils tolerance ^a		Al toxicity tolerance	P deficiency tolerance	Fe toxicity tolerance
	1 mo	2 mo			
Bâu	1	1	1	1	1-2
IR2151-96-1-5-2	1	2	1	1	3-4
IR2153-26-3-5-6	2	3	3	3	4
A4	2	3	3	3	2-4
B9C-Md-3-3	3	3	3	3	4
424 (NN75-2)	1	5	1	1	5
B541-bkn52-3-3	5	3	5	3	4-5
IR1529-680-3-2	5	4	5	5	3-5
IR42	5	6	3	3	5
IR46	5	7	3	3	5
386 (NN75-7)	5	7	5	1	3
IR9575	7	5	5	3	3
IR4683-54-3-3-2	—	—	5	3	7
IR2797-105-2-2-3	—	—	5	3	7
IR8	7	5	7	5	5

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = growth and tillering nearly normal; 5 = growth and tillering retarded, many leaves discolored; 9 = almost all plants dead or dying.

in saline soils. IR2151, with tolerance for P deficiency and resistance to brown planthopper biotype 1, also is accepted in regions where IR8 cannot be cultivated. ■

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